

Evaluation of Utilization of Nursing Process and Creation of Atmosphere of Trust in Federal School of Psychiatric Nursing Programme, Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study evaluated utilization of nursing process and creation of atmosphere of trust in Federal School of Psychiatric Nursing Programme Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. Two research questions were raised to direct the course of this study. An evaluation research design was adopted to evaluate 64 psychiatric nurses purposively selected from the 150 students who graduated from the School between 2014-2019 working in Federal Neuro-Psychiatric Hospital, Calabar. Data was collected using observational technique and checklist designed by the researcher. The instrument was validated and reliability established with the use of Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Same was corrected with Spearman Brown prophecy formula. The reliability coefficient ranged from 0.810-0.990. Analysis was done using descriptive statistics which involve proportion, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and weighted mean. Findings of the study revealed that nurses from Federal School of Psychiatric Nursing, Calabar fairly utilize their nursing process and had overall good performance in creating an atmosphere of trust, which allows for meeting the patient's basic emotional needs. It was therefore concluded that nurses utilized nursing process in providing comprehensive mental health nursing care to individuals and families whether at primary, secondary or tertiary healthcare settings. They also create an atmosphere of trust, which allows for meeting the patient's basic emotional needs. Based on these findings, it was recommended among others that the school should include the program objectives in their curriculum, increase supervision of students during clinical on use of nursing process and ensure enough nursing project booklets are reproduced for use in the school and clinical area.

Keywords: Evaluation; Nursing Process; Atmosphere of Trust; Psychiatric Nursing Program.

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INTRODUCTION

Education is as old as man and its usefulness is significant to both ancient and modern societies. It is a springboard of socio-economic growth and development of every society and nation. Education equips an individual to face future life challenges and expectations and provide him with equitable response accepted by the environment and people whom he relates daily. One of the factors that enhance education is the general good health of the learners. Hence, people learn well when all levels of wellness is attained in compliance with the definition of health, that “health is a state of complete physical, emotional, mental, social and spiritual wellness, and not merely the absent of illness”. Mental health being an integral component of wellbeing is of utmost priority in attaining learning.

Accordingly, mental illness is a condition that worries and remains mysterious to many countries including Nigeria for many years before Colonial Regime. Psychiatric practice was introduced to handle diagnosis, treatment, prevention and rehabilitation of abnormal behaviors. This involves separation of psychiatric patients from others with general physiological disorders so as to accord them their special care and attention. It therefore requires training of the nurse who is the immediate caregiver and establishment of School of Psychiatric Nursing in the country.

The Federal Government through Federal Ministry of Health in cooperation with Nursing and Midwifery Council of Nigeria category ‘B’ established eight (8) Schools of Psychiatry Nursing across the country under Decree No. 89 of 1979, now known as Nursing and Midwifery Act. Cap. N143, Laws of Federation of Nigeria, 2004. In that line, School of Psychiatric Nursing Calabar was founded in 1980 under Mr. Udo Benjamin Ikpe who was the Head of Nursing Services.

As contained in NMCN (2016), School of Psychiatric Nursing Program is a national program designed by Nursing and Midwifery Council of Nigeria (NMCN) for all states running the program with same curriculum and syllabus. At the end of one year six (1.6) month’s duration, it is expected that all graduating students should be able to:

- I. Utilize nursing process to provide comprehensive mental health nursing care to individuals and families whether at primary, secondary or tertiary healthcare settings.
- II. Provide a therapeutic environment conducive to reconciliation and incorporation of patients to the social norms of the community through intersectoral team approach.
- III. Provide a safe physical setting which minimizes the pathological stress related to illness.
- IV. Create an atmosphere of trust, which allows for meeting the patient’s basic emotional needs.
- V. Encourage individuals and establish opportunities for self-expression, self-acceptance and self-evaluation which will encourage the acceptance of responsibilities commensurate with changing capacities.

- VI. Display tolerance in accepting maladaptive behavior of the patient.
- VII. Assist in providing the necessary corrective experiences for redirection of negative behaviors to achieve personal growth.

Based on above background, school of psychiatric nursing has to lay emphasis on development of content and syllabus in line with theoretical and practical aspect of nursing. The aim of the program was to train nurses on how to diagnose, treat, prevent and rehabilitate the mentally ill in psychiatric hospitals and communities (Ikpe&Ekpo, 2012). In Federal Neuro-Psychiatric Hospital, most psychiatric patient has been mentally stabilized to resume their daily activities and official engagement within and outside the state. In the year 2000 when Nigeria hosted world beauty competition, street lunatics were swept and managed in the facility. Out of the 106 cases, 72 were claimed home by the relatives having been confirmed mentally fit to relate with the society. The other 26 who had no relation within Calabar were tactfully returned to their family members through internal repatriation scheme. In confirmation of their functionality, the remaining eight (8) were trained in Occupational Therapy on the skill of their best fit. Moreover, long stay and abandoned ones have their mind occupied with art, games and vocation till identified with the family. This was achieved through OT prescriptions aimed at intimating patient's motor and sensory units that coordinate functions, thus preventing atrophy, contractures and complications of blood circulation. With these psychiatric student nurses were equipped to be good ambassadors of the institution by rendering effective mental health care services to any society they find themselves.

However, being that the success of nursing program depends on societal acceptance in line with set objectives, there is need for process of the school program to be evaluated after forty-three (43) years of operation. This is due to the fact that evaluation performs essential role in program's improvement (Yoloye, 2008). The essence is to provide feedback regarding the program's strength or weakness; and appropriate corrective measures in other to attain the programs' goal and objectives. According to Andales (2018), product evaluation is a means to investigate how intervention works, their interventions and how they interact with objectives. It considers which value to be derived from study, how to achieve them, how to use the knowledge, what suitable method could be used and whether if useful socio-technical applications are introduced produce future value or harm. The assessment was to ascertain suitability and safety of end products for use by consumers. It is conducted for two major reasons: to ensure standardization of process of attaining the product, and to identify and remove unwanted practice and defects between product attainment. This is because failure to identify product and design defects can result in products' objection and litigation. Product evaluation therefore provides basis for continual monitoring, formulation and reformation of program. In education, evaluation of school program is to determine the extent to which it has served the purpose which it was established. In situations where product evaluation is not carried out, there is possibility of risk of failure. Where it is periodically conducted, it enhances improvement, efficiency and accountability.

In Psychiatric Hospital Calabar, concern is expressed by management staff, nursing unit heads and patients' relatives about poor service delivery of nursing care. These ranges from lateness to work, absenteeism, insubordination, poor documentation of events, non-

recording of clinical findings, disregard and non-concern for patients among other misconducts.

There is however no need to pretend about complaints of poor quality of psychiatric nursing service as the old nurses are regarded to be more reliable than the young breeds (FNPH/NAR/Vol.1/P.43). This makes the image of profession to reduce as a nurse has no interest over the condition of patients. Therefore, through forms of monitoring and evaluation it is possible to determine whether the school has achieved its objectives or not (Yoloye, 2008). It is also observed that since the school was established in 1980, there had been no empirical work conducted by individual or authorities to ascertain attainment of its designed objectives. Hence it is imperative to conduct product evaluation of graduating students of this school in other to fill the research gab.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Utilization of Nursing Process

Nursing process is the recent accepted approach considered appropriate for explanation, application and rendition of nursing action to the sick in the contemporary era. It was first used by Northern American Nursing Association and having been proven best scientific approach, it's adopted in every health setting to provide healthcare as an ideology for nursing professionalism (Hagos, Alemseged, Belcha, Berha & Aregay, 2012). It is a dynamic and systematic way of delivering care with five interrelated steps: assessment, diagnosis, planning, outcome identification, implementation and evaluation (Pokorski, Moraes, Chiarelli, Costanzi & Rabelo, 2009). Effective implementation of nursing process results in improved quality of nursing care and enhances formulation of theories and scientific knowledge to the best clinical practice (Birhanu, Assefa, Woldie & Morankar, 2010).

Issue lies on its global adoption by various institutions as it requires nurses' acknowledgement and team work amidst limitations of finance, hospital policies and local dilemmas in attempt to accomplish research study through it.

In another cross-sectional survey by Aseratie, Murugan and Molla (2014), it was discovered that organizational factors, patient's related issues, practicing skills and level of knowledge influence implementation of nursing process at government hospitals of Addis Ababa and Ethiopia. This was evidence to the authors as Nurses work under stressful conditions, lack of time to apply the principles, worsened with poor knowledge and gender disparity.

Report from Nursing Administration of the school service area disclosed empty and blank unfilled nursing process booklet unutilized by students and nursing staff of the facility. This gave students ground to pay deaf ear at observation, documentation and studying patient's problems along medical directives to establish baseline for nursing action (Nursing Administration and Research/Federal Psychiatric Hospital, Calabar, 2017).

According to Beck (2013), psychiatric nurses are handicap of formulating nursing diagnosis according to patients' problem. The ill aspect of it is that they are not interested in learning and utilizing others' creative ideas. Hence, one of the hindering factor is how to coin a suitable nursing diagnose into patients' presenting complaints before setting a compatible

action to tackle the situation. This collaborates with assertions of Beck (2013) who revealed that nurses face unique challenges in applying nursing process due to vagueness of patient's emotional problems which might have different problems and causes. In the same vein, any obvious manifestation of a psychiatric patient may originate from several repressed experiences which patient could not explain. They may also be unable to participate in problem solving process when they are anxious, withdrawn or far from reality.

In a study conducted by Agyeman-Yeboah, Korsah and Okrah (2017) on exploration of various factors that influence utilization of nursing process at Accra—Ghana, an exploratory descriptive qualitative-research design was employed. Ten participants were involved using purposive sampling method. A semi-structured interview guide was used to collect the data from the research participants; and the data were analyzed by using content analysis. The result revealed that there are factors responsible for the non-utilization. And one of the factors was nurses not having a better understanding of the nursing process. The non-awareness prevails whilst in school and extends to service area where there was absence of care plan in the ward, as well as lack of adequate staff, with limited time being available for coping. These contributed to the non-usage of the nursing process.

Another empirical study conducted by Hagos, Alemseged, Balcha, Berhe and Aregay (2012), was to assess the application of nursing process and its affecting factors in Mekelle Zone Hospitals. They used a cross sectional design employing quantitative and qualitative methods. Qualitative data was obtained from 14 nursing heads of six hospitals and quantitative data obtained from 200 nurses using simple random sampling technique from the six hospitals proportional to their size. Thematic and SPSS version 16.1 analysis were used for quantitative and qualitative data respectively. The result revealed that 90% of respondents had poor knowledge, 99.5% had positive attitude towards nursing process, 75% of respondents said nurse-to-patient ratio was not enough to apply nursing process, while all respondents responded that they had not used nursing process in provision of care to any patient within the zone at the time of study. It was therefore recommended that hospitals should consider application of nursing process critical in their zone, motivate nurses and monitor its application in progress.

Creation of Atmosphere of Trust

Existence of confidence, reliability, veracity, integrity and sincere desire to provide required needs are qualities found in a nurse that wins a patient's trust. It is demonstrated through nursing interventions which convey sense of warmth and care to a patient. Townsend, (2011) illustrated various conditions that permit trust as: providing blanket to a patient under cold weather, providing food to a hungry patient, keeping to promise, showing honesty, providing cogent explanation and reasons to procedure, rules and philosophy, adherence to institutional policies and guidelines, and taking patients' preference, opinion and request.

Andvig, Syse and Severinsson (2014) in their qualitative study at Norway, described and interpret the existent of inter-personal collaboration and a trusty atmosphere existing among their healthcare givers and the psychiatric patients through dialogue. The researchers disclosed that this was possible through acknowledgement, understanding and strengthening

of professionals by their institutional employers so as to improve their quality of service. In the other vain, Magnusson and Lützén (2009) detect mistrust and lack of collaboration between Community Mental Healthcare and her psychiatric patients due to different ideologies of care and objectives. This was realized from poor collaboration of effort and non-use of another's competence leading to increase relapse and long stay. In the same healthcare when trust and collaborative network was re-established between community staff, in-patients and discharged patients, case of relapsed and readmission reduced and quality of life improved (Fernandes & Flak (2012). In a trusty atmosphere, members possess the following characteristic: common goals, performs task relevant to goal attainment, independent existence, undertaking diverse roles and responsibilities toward patient's welfare (Kozłowski & Ilgen, 2006). Best of all, they survive on information sharing, smooth communication, participatory decision-making, practices, developing new ideas, and organizing treatment delivery programs.

According to Borg, Karlsson, Tondora, and Davidson (2009), a trusty healthcare facility is concerned with person-centered healthcare which is known for provision of individualized care quite congruent with patient's needs, desire and preferences.

Empirically, Tuveesson, Wann-Hansson and Eklund (2011) conducted study on importance of the ward atmosphere of psychosocial work environment of nursing staff in psychiatric in-patient care at Sweden with 93 from 12 general psychiatric wards. The study used two questionnaires to compare activities of nurses and nursing assistants towards maintenance of trust in psychiatric ward. Obtained data was analyzed with descriptive statistics, Mann-Whitney U-test, Spearman rank correlations and forward stepwise conditional logistic regression analyses. The result revealed that there were no differences between nurses and nurse assistants concerning perceptions of the psychosocial work environment and the ward atmosphere of trust.

Lok and Buldukoglu (2015) carried out a study on the effect of therapeutic atmosphere on social functionality of in-patients in a University Psychiatry Clinic in Akdeniz. The study was a descriptive cross-sectional and relational study using 50 patients who accepted to participate in the study and who had been hospitalized in the Psychiatric Hospital. The demographic data was analyzed using percentages, Friedman Test in repeated measures to compare the social functionality scores of the patients in three different times, while Kruskal Wallis test was used to evaluate the relation between the social functionality scores and demographic data of the patients. Also, Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test the relationship between scores of social functional and ward atmosphere scores. Results of the study revealed that the patients evaluated the ward atmosphere higher than the average in terms of participation, spontaneity, autonomy, practical intention, anger and aggression, order and organization, clarity of the program, and staff control. On the whole, there was a significant positive correlation between social functionality scores and the participants' perception regarding ward atmosphere. It was also determined that participation was positively and strongly correlated with spare-time activities while spontaneity was positively and moderately correlated with interpersonal functionality, spare-time activities and independence (competence). With this the authors concluded that the current atmosphere of trust in-cooperated in psychiatric clinic was found to increase social functionality of the patients and mutual coexistence.

Achieving above will promote principles of therapeutic milieu which is essential component of hospitalization period for patients to take advantage to meet their needs. Therapeutic milieu is the base of activities of psychiatric nurses. This term are used to describe the atmosphere in which all the resources should be arranged for providing optimal care for patients. The major components of therapeutic milieu are security, structure, norms, limits, balance and flexibility. Nurses are the shapers, leaders and users of the milieu. So, being therapeutic or non-therapeutic of the milieu depends on nurse's skills and interests.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts evaluation research design. According to Powel (2006), it is concerned with the type of structure created to provide needed answers to research questions which must be made to align with the program theory of change and logic model. The study was conducted on Federal School of Psychiatric Nursing situated at Mary Slesor Avenue in Calabar Metropolis. The population of this study consists of 150 graduate nurses of School of Psychiatric Nursing from 2014 to 2019. The numbers of graduate were 30 for each year and when summed up for the 5 batches it brings the population of study to 150 graduates. These data were obtained from the Admission Register of School of Psychiatric Nursing, Calabar, 2020. Purposive sampling technique was used for the study. This is because this number of nurses qualified within the period of 2014-2019 and could best serve the purpose, being the current and newest batch with fresh skill and knowledge. Others within the batch are working as psychiatric nurses at General Hospital Calabar, University of Calabar Teaching Hospital, Navy Hospital Calabar, outside the state and outside the country. The researcher selected 64 newly qualified psychiatric nurses who graduated from class 2014-2019 batches in Federal School of Psychiatric nursing, Calabar and who were gainfully employed into service of Federal Neuro-Psychiatric Hospital, Calabar. This group of products was useful and accessible to the researcher since they were working with the researcher in the same institution and are practicing pure psychiatric nursing.

The instrument titled "Checklist and Observation Scale for Product Evaluation of Federal School of Psychiatric Nursing in Calabar" (COSPEFSPN) was used for data collection. It involved a structured participatory observational schedule with rating scale, drawn on the variables under investigation.

Section 'A' was used to record information on demographic data of the nurse, the researcher used observation checklist to obtain data in sections B. Section B consist of 10 items with information on the respondents' utilization of nursing process using a four point Likert-type scale of fully utilized (FU), utilized (U), underutilized (UN) and unutilized (UU) for variable one; and a 7-points rating scale rated from 1 to 7 for the second variable.

The type of validity adopted for the study was face and content validity. Face validity considers the outward appearance of a test instrument to ascertain whether it resembles a valid measuring tool. On the other hand, content validity considers the possibility with which the test item appropriately represents the knowledge area which the test was designed for.

The reliability estimate of the instrument was determined through split half reliability by conducting a trial test using thirty-five (35) psychiatric graduate nurses working in Federal

Psychiatric Hospital Calabar, who were not included in the study. The obtained reliability coefficient ranged from 0.810-0.990, indicating its suitability and consistency over time for use in rating nurses' procedures.

To facilitate data collection, a total of 64 copies of the instruments was printed and used for observing and rating qualified nurses. The researcher recruited four psychiatric nurses to assist in the process. After collecting and gathering the instruments from research assistants, they were sorted and coded for easy analysis, and scores were assigned to each item. For ease of procedure, coding schedule was prepared by developing a key for each of the construct of the instruments. A descriptive statistic with percentages and charts were the means of data analysis.

Presentation of results

Research question 1: To what extent do nurses utilize nursing process in providing comprehensive mental health nursing care to individuals and families whether at primary, secondary or tertiary healthcare settings? To answer this research question, Frequency counts, simple percentages, mean and standard deviation was adopted.

The first objective of the study was to find out whether products (nurses) of Federal School of Psychiatric Nursing are competent in the use of nursing process in providing holistic care to psychiatric patients. Items measuring this objective were structured using 4-points Likert type scale of; unutilized, underutilized, utilized, and fully utilized. Accordingly, scores were awarded as follows: 0 – for unutilized; 1 – for underutilized, 2 – for utilized, and 3 – for fully utilized. A total of ten (10) items were used in measuring this variable; hence, the minimum score for a participant was zero (0) while the maximum score was 3. The 10 items include: Assessment sheet, state of health, Nursing history, mental state examination, physical examination, admission history, Nursing care plan, daily reporting, discharge summary, and follow-up care. Results of the descriptive statistics presented in Table 1 shows that a mean score of 15.83 ± 2.89 was obtained for all the 64 nurses used for this study. According to the Table, the obtained mean score falls between the score range of participants with fair utilization of nursing care process. Hence, it is concluded that the products of Federal School of Psychiatric Nursing fairly utilize nursing care process in providing care to psychiatric patients.

The performance of the participants based on the respective aspects of assessment is presented in Figure 1. As presented in the chart, decisions are made based on the relative distance of a point from the red bold line which divides the chart into two equal parts. Accordingly, all aspects above the red line are adjudged to be good while all aspects below the line are adjudged to be poor. It is also worthy of note that items closer to the line are adjudged to be fair, that is either fairly good (for items above the line) or fairly poor (for items below the line). Based on these descriptions, nurses' performance on "nursing care plan" and "discharge summary" was very poor (0.31 ± 0.64), and there is an overall poor performance on "follow-up care" (0.84 ± 0.99) among the nurses. On the other-hand, the nurses' performance on "admission history" was very good (2.80 ± 0.41), while their performance on "daily reporting" was good (2.31 ± 0.83), and their overall performance on aspects including; assessment sheet (1.81 ± 0.97), state of health (1.76 ± 0.92), nursing history

(1.83±0.83), mental state examination (1.92±0.90), and physical examination (1.76±0.61), were fairly good.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics showing the summary of participants’ use of nursing process in the care of patients (N=64)

Utilization of Nursing Care Process	No. of Nurses assessed	Percentage (%)	Score Range	Mean ($\bar{x}$)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Good	6	9.4	21 – 30	21.00	0.00
Fair	58	90.6	11 – 20	15.29	2.47
Poor	-	-	0 – 10	0.00	0.00
Total	64	100	0 – 30	15.83	2.89

Figure 1: Nurses performance on the respective items measuring utilization of nursing process

Research question 2: To what extent do nurses create an atmosphere of trust, which allows for meeting the patient’s basic emotional needs? To answer this research question, Frequency counts, simple percentages, mean and standard deviation was adopted. Creating an atmosphere of trust which allows for meeting the patient’s basic emotional needs

The second objective of this study was to assess how products (Nurses) of Federal School of Psychiatric Nursing are competent in creating an atmosphere of trust to enhance mutual relationship between themselves and their patients. This variable was measured using 10 items structured on a 7-points rating scale and rated from 1 to 7. Therefore, the minimum score of a participant was 10 while the maximum score was 70. The 10 items used for this assessment were: creating mutual relationship, explanation of every procedure to patients, respect of patient’s opinion and rights, attention to patient’s needs and complaints, effective

nurse-patient relationship, provision of patients with right information, preservation of patient’s secrecy, establishing a friendly relationship with patient and family members, keeping of promise to patient, and ability to advocate for patient’s need. A descriptive summary statistic of this variable is presented in Table 2. The Table shows that the mean score (55.86 ± 6.96) obtained for all the assessed nurses falls within the score range of the category described as good with regards to the investigated variable. Hence, it is inferred that products of Federal School of Psychiatric Nursing are good in creating an atmosphere of trust necessary to boost mutual relationship between them and patients.

Also, Figure 2 presents the performance of the nurses based on the respective items of the assessment. The trend of the line graph indicates that the least performed items were creating and maintaining an effective nurse-patient relationship (5.41 ± 1.19) closely followed by keeping of promises to the patients (5.45 ± 0.96), while the most performed of the 10 items was preservation of patients’ secrecy (5.75 ± 0.78). On the whole, the mean weighted scores obtained for the items indicate that nurses displayed good performance on all the assessed items.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics showing the summary of participants’ competence in creating an atmosphere of trust which allows for meeting the patient’s basic emotional needs (N=64)

Creation of atmosphere of trust for mutual relationship	No. of Nurses assessed	Percentage (%)	Score Range	Mean ($\bar{x}$)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Good	51	83.6	51 – 70	58.59	4.25
Fair	13	16.4	31 – 50	45.15	4.86
Poor	-	-	10 – 30	0.00	0.00
Total	64	100	10 – 70	55.86	6.96

Figure 2: Nurses performance on creation of atmosphere of trust

Discussion of findings

Use of nursing process in providing health care to psychiatric patients

Results of this evaluation study revealed that the assessed nurses display fairly good performance on aspects such as; the use of assessment sheet, assessing patients' state of health, putting up nursing history, carrying out patients' mental state examination, and carrying out physical examination of the patients; while their performance on taking of patients' history during admission was very good. However, the nurses had an overall poor performance on implementing follow-up care for discharged patients, and exhibited very poor performance on aspects including, implementation of the nursing care plan, and putting up discharge summary for patients who are discharged. On the whole, a summary of the descriptive statistics revealed that the mean competence score of the assessed nurses in the use of nursing process falls within the category of fair competence. Therefore, it was inferred that products of Federal School of Psychiatric Nursing in Calabar are fairly competent in the use of nursing process in providing health care to psychiatric patients.

The finding of this study as reported above is supported by a 2017 report of the Nursing Administration and Research of the Federal Neuropsychiatric Hospital, Calabar. This report holds that most times student nurses do not utilize the nursing process booklet; hence, these booklets were found blank and unfilled. Similarly, Becks (2013) found that psychiatric nursing students were not fully competent in formulating nursing diagnosis in line with patients' problems which agrees with findings of the present study.

Hagos et al (2012) in a study to assess the application of nursing care process among nurses in Mekelle Zone Hospital, found that almost all the nurses used for the study reported non-usage of the nursing process in provision of care to any patient within the zone as at the time of the study. However, the nurses assessed in this study despite the fair usage had utilized the nursing care process in providing care to patients. Hence, finding as reported by Hagos et al (2012) contradicts the findings of this present study as their respondents did not utilize the nursing care process at all.

Creating an atmosphere of trust which allows for meeting the patient's basic emotional needs

The second objective of the study sought to establish the competence of the assessed nurses in creating an atmosphere of trust which allows for meeting the patient's basic emotional needs. Findings of the study as presented in the preceding section revealed that the nurses displayed good performance in all aspects of the assessment. That is, the nurses were good at creating and maintaining effective nurse-patient relationship, kept promises to patients, pay attention to patients' needs and compliant, respect the rights and opinion of the patients, giving adequate explanation of procedures to patients, preserve patients' secrecy, and maintained friendly relationship with patients and family members. The most performed aspect of this assessment was the preservation of patients' secrecy. In summary, the mean competence score of the nurses which falls within the score range of good competence revealed that the products of Federal School of Psychiatric Nursing, Calabar are good in

creating atmosphere of trust to foster mutual relationship between themselves and their clients.

This finding is in tandem with findings of Andvig et al (2014) who reported that inter-personal collaboration and a trusty atmosphere exist between healthcare providers and psychiatric patients in psychiatric health facilities in Norway. Also, in a study to assess the effect of therapeutic atmosphere on social functionality of in-patients in a University Psychiatry Clinic in Akdeniz, LokandBuldukoglu (2015), submitted that nurses create an atmosphere of trust in the psychiatric clinic which was found to increase social functionality of the patients and foster mutual co-existence between the patients and the nurses.

However, Magnusson and Lütznén (2009) found mistrust and lack of collaboration between Community Mental Healthcare providers and psychiatric patients due to poor collaboration of effort and non-use of another's competence and which led to increase relapse and long stay among the patients. This report disagrees with findings of this study as the assessed nurses were found competent in creating an atmosphere of trust to enhance mutual relationship between them and the patients.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that nurses of Federal School of Psychiatric Nursing are fairly competent in utilizing their nursing process to provide care to the mentally ill. Nevertheless, nurses utilized nursing process in providing comprehensive mental health nursing care to individuals and families whether at primary, secondary or tertiary healthcare settings. They also create an atmosphere of trust, which allows for meeting the patient's basic emotional needs.

Recommendations

The following recommendation is given to the Management of School and Nursing Department of Federal Psychiatric Hospital Calabar:

1. Structure the academic curriculum to involve the programme objectives laid down by Nursing and Midwifery Council of Nigeria (NMCN).
2. Introduce use of nursing process as a course of lecture in class curriculum.
3. Reinforce supervision of students during clinical practice on utilization of nursing process.
4. Reiterate lists of nursing diagnoses domicile in psychiatry for clinical use.
5. Reproduction of more nursing process booklet sufficient for students in class and clinical practice.

REFERENCE

- Agyeman-Yeboah, J., Korsah, K. & Okrah, J. (2017). Factors that influence the clinical utilization of the nursing process at a hospital in Accre, Ghana. *BCM Nursing Journal*, 16 (30):
- Andales, J. (2018). Product evaluation template. *Auditor*, SafetyCulture, Manila, 2018. <https://safetyculture.com/checklists/product-evaluation/>
- Andvig, E.; Syse, J. & Severinsson, E. (2014). Interprofessional collaboration in the mental health services in Norway, *Nursing Research and Practice*, Volume 2014, Article ID 849375, 8 pages, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2014/849375>
- Aseratie, M.; Murugan, R. & Molla, M. (2014). Assessment of factors affecting implementation of nursing process among nurses in selected governmental hospitals, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia: Cross sectional study. *J Nurs Care* 3:170. doi:10.4172/2167-1168.1000170
- Beck, J. (2013). Nursing Process in Psychiatry Nursing, *Psychiatric Nursing*, open access articles on mental health
- Birhanu, Z.; Assefa, T.; Woldie, M. & Morankar, S. (2010). Determinants of satisfaction with health care provider interactions at health centres in central Ethiopia: A cross sectional study. *BMC Health Services Research*, 10, article 78
- Borg, M.; Karlsson, B.; Tondora, J. & Davidson, L. (2009). "Implementing person-centered care in psychiatric rehabilitation: What does this involve?" *Israel Journal of Psychiatry and Related Sciences*. Vol. 46, no. 2, pp. 84–93.
- Fernandes, V. & Flak, E. (2012). Safe and effective prescribing practices at the point of discharge from an inpatient psychiatric unit. *J Psychiatr Pract*. 2012 Jan;18(1):12-9. doi:10.1097/01.pra.0000410983.08229.d0.
- FNPH, (2012). Your Leadership Style, Laudable. The Bulletin of the Federal Neuro-Psychiatric Hospital, Calabar. Vol.1-No. 3, P.13
- Hagos, F.; Alemseged, F.; Balcha, F.; Berhe, S. & Aregay, A. (2014). Application of nursing process and its affecting factors among nurses working in Mekelle Zone Hospitals, Northern Ethiopia, Vol. (2014), Art. ID (675212), pp. 8, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/675212>
- Ikpe, E. B. and Ekpo, M. (2012). The Federal Neuro-Psychiatric Hospital, Calabar, From premier lunatic asylum to Teaching Hospital 1903-2003. Published by Best print business press-publishing company, Uyo, Akwalbom state-Nigeria. Printed by Infinitikoncepts. Pp. 143-145. ISBN: 97805496683
- Kozlowski, S. & Ilgen, D. (2006). "Enhancing the effectiveness of work groups and teams". *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 77–124, 2006.

- Lok, N. & Buldukoglu, K. (2015). Effect of Therapeutic Atmosphere in a Psychiatric Clinic on Social Functionality of in-patients, *Journal of Psychiatry*, ISSN: 2378-5756.
- Magnusson, A. & Lützn, K. (2009). "Factors that influence collaboration between psychiatric care and CSSs: Experiences of working together in the interest of persons with long-term mental illness living in the community," *Scandinavian Journal of Caring Sciences*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 140–145, 2009.
- National Institute of Mental Health, (2016). Suicide prevention. National Suicide Prevention Lifeline (Lifeline) at 1-800-273-TALK (8255).
<https://www.nimh.nih.gov/health/topics/suicide-prevention/>
- Nelson, S. (2017). Product evaluation. Chris Nagar College of education,
<https://www.slideshare.net/sheebar62/product-evaluation-82536273>
- Nursing & Midwifery Council of Nigeria (NMCN), (2016). Mental health and psychiatric nursing curriculum, Revised (2016). Pp. 2-3
- Pokorski, S.; Moraes, M. A.; Chiarelli, R.; Costanzi, A. P. & Rabelo, E. R. (2009). Nursing process: from literature to practice. What are we actually doing? *Revista Latino-Americana de Enfermagem*. 2009;17(3):302–307.
- Townsend, M. (2011). Psychiatric mental health nursing. F. A. Davis Company, 1915 Arch Street, Philadelphia. Nursing: Martone, R., Editor. Nursing: Tom Ciavarella. Interior Designer: Paul Fry. Cover designer: Emily Betch, United State of America
- Townsend, M. (2013), Essentials of Psychiatric Mental Health Nursing: Concepts of Care in Evidence based Practice, 6th Edition, F.A. Davis Company, 2013, ISBN 0803638760, 9780803638761
- Turesson, H.; Wann-Hansson, C. & Eklund, M. (2011). The ward atmosphere important for the psychosocial work environment of nursing staff in psychiatric in-patient care, *BCM Nursing* volume 10, article number 12 (2011).
- Yoloye, E. A. (2008). Fundamentals of educational evaluation. Starling-Horden publishers Ltd., Gaaf Building, 110-112 Oyo Road, Oyo State, Ibadan. Phone: 08023519154. E-mail: horden@skannet.com.